

FREQUENCY OF EXTENSIVELY DRUG RESISTANT (XDR) IN PATIENT WITH TYPHOID FEVER AT TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL SUKKUR

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: Extensively drug-resistant (XDR) typhoid fever is an emerging public health threat in Pakistan, with rising resistance to multiple antibiotics. This study aimed to determine the frequency of extensively drug resistant (XDR) in patient with typhoid fever presented to a tertiary care teaching hospital in Sukkur.

METHODOLOGY: A cross-sectional study was conducted on 134 patients aged 18-60 years, diagnosed with typhoid fever. Antibiotic sensitivity testing was used to identify XDR typhoid, defined as resistance to ampicillin, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, fluoroquinolones, and third-generation cephalosporins. Data on socio-demographic factors, comorbidities, vaccination status, and laboratory findings were collected. Chi-square and Fisher's exact tests were applied to assess associations, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

RESULTS: XDR typhoid was identified in 80 patients (59.7%). Statistically significant associations were observed between XDR typhoid and urban residence ($p=0.001$), male gender ($p=0.048$), low educational status ($p=0.003$), hypertension ($p=0.004$), diabetes mellitus ($p=0.001$), obesity ($p=0.001$), smoking ($p=0.002$), low platelet count ($p<0.001$), anemia ($p=0.010$), vitamin D deficiency ($p<0.001$), and lack of typhoid vaccination ($p<0.001$). Age and marital status were not significantly associated with XDR typhoid.

CONCLUSION: The high burden of XDR typhoid underscores the urgent need for public health interventions, including rational antibiotic use, improved sanitation, health education, and widespread typhoid vaccination. Early identification of high-risk individuals and addressing modifiable risk factors can help curb the spread of drug-resistant Salmonella typhi strains.

INTRODUCTION

Enteric fever, comprising both typhoid and paratyphoid fever, is a serious systemic infection caused by *Salmonella enterica* serotypes Typhi and Paratyphi, respectively [1]. It remains a significant public health challenge in many low- and middle-income countries, where its impact is amplified by rapid population growth, inadequate urban planning, poor sanitation, and unsafe water supplies [2, 3]. Globally, an estimated 11 to 21 million cases of typhoid fever occur annually, resulting in approximately 128,000 to 161,000 deaths [4].

In South Asia, the burden of enteric fever is especially pronounced. Among regional countries, Pakistan reports the highest incidence, with rates as high as 451.7 per 100,000 population per year, compared to 214.2 per 100,000 in India [5, 6]. In 2018, Pakistan recorded an alarming incidence of 493.5 cases per 100,000, underscoring the endemic nature of typhoid in the country.⁷

A particularly concerning development has been the emergence of extensively drug-resistant (XDR) *Salmonella* Typhi, first identified during an outbreak in Hyderabad, Sindh, in 2016 [7]. This resistant strain is unresponsive to conventional antibiotics such as chloramphenicol, ampicillin, co-trimoxazole, fluoroquinolones, and third-generation cephalosporins, leaving limited treatment options like azithromycin, carbapenems, and tigecycline [7].

According to data from the National Institute of Health (NIH) Islamabad, between January 2017 and June 2021, over 14,360 cases of XDR typhoid were reported in Karachi. During the same period, an additional 5,741 cases were recorded across other districts in Sindh, with nearly 70% originating from Hyderabad district alone [8, 9].

Studies have highlighted a disturbing trend in resistance patterns. The proportion of multidrug-resistant (MDR) typhoid has surged from 34.2% to 64.1%, while XDR typhoid was reported in 64.1% of cases by Pustake et al. and 54% by Batool et al [10, 11]. Similarly, Fatima et al. documented a prevalence of 66% XDR during their study conducted between 2016 and 2018 [12].

Despite these concerning statistics, there is a lack of updated data from the interior regions of Sindh, where diagnostic infrastructure is limited, and empirical treatments are common. Given the

evolving nature of antimicrobial resistance and the potential for misuse of antibiotics in rural settings, continuous surveillance is critical.

This study was designed to evaluate the prevalence and antibiotic resistance patterns of *Salmonella* Typhi strains isolated from blood or stool cultures of patients presenting with enteric fever in a peripheral tehsil of Sindh. By identifying the local frequency of XDR strains, the findings aim to assist clinicians in selecting appropriate empirical therapies and inform public health authorities on the urgent need for preventive strategies. The results could also raise awareness about the growing threat of waterborne and foodborne infections and the importance of targeted interventions in rural communities. Thus the study was conducted to determine the frequency of extensively drug resistant (XDR) in patient with typhoid fever.

PATIENTS AND METHODS: The three months cross sectional study (from 28-Feb-2025 to 27-May-2025) was conducted in the Department of Medicine at Ghulam Mohammad Mahar Medical College (GMMMC) Hospital Sukkur. The sample size was calculated by taken the lowest proportion of extensively drug resistant in typhoid fever (66%) [12]; $d = 8\%$, $n = 134$ patients had typhoid fever were recruited by non-probability consecutive sampling.

The study was conducted after the approval by CPSP on the subjects fulfilled the inclusion criteria and by taking informed consent.

The inclusion criteria of the study were The patient of 18-60 years of age, either gender with clinically diagnosed case of typhoid fever (defined as a fever of 38 degree centigrade or above for 3 or more days) along with complain / history of symptoms as nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, constipation along with positive blood / stool culture.

The exclusion criteria were the patients known case of dengue and malaria, individuals already on corticosteroids, immune-suppressive therapy, and known cases of malignancies (colorectal, leukemia and lymphomas), the pregnant and lactating ladies, and patients taking antibiotics before presenting to hospital within 7 days.

All the patients presented thru out-patient department (OPD) and diagnosed as typhoid fever [by culture-positive had *S. typhi* growth (1 or more

colonies), obtained from blood culture or/and stool culture after a maximum of 7 days of sample incubation in the laboratory] were further evaluated for the for blood culture / sensitivity by taking 10 cc venous blood sample in a disposable syringe and sent to the laboratory. The senior pathologist had more than 05 years clinical laboratory experience was analyzed the specimen. The extensively drug resistant (XDR) was labeled as by determining the sensitivity and resistance of antibiotics and the XDR was considered as resistant to fluoroquinolones and third-generation cephalosporin (ceftriaxone) in addition to ampicillin, chloramphenicol, and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. The laboratory test as culture and sensitivity report was clear to inform that which drugs is sensitive (S) and which one is resistant (R). The data was collected on pre-designed proforma as per study variables whereas all the financial burden of the study were paid by researcher himself.

The effects modifiers were also explored as;

Hypertension: labeled as measuring blood pressure ($\geq 140/90$) on presentation

Smoking: smoking [had history of tobacco use (≥ 5 cigarettes per day) for ≥ 02 years duration (on clinical history)] while the ex-smoking' refers to someone who had smoked more than 100 cigarettes in their lifetime but has not smoked in the last 28 days.

Obesity: when BMI ≥ 27.5 kg/m² and low platelet count: less than 150,000 platelets per microliter of blood.

Diabetes mellitus: blood glucose level ≥ 200 mg/dl and HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$ regardless of treatment.

Anemia: less than 12 g/dL in females and less than 13 g/dL in males

Vitamin D deficiency: The serum vitamin D level < 20 ng/mL

Vaccination status: categorized as vaccinated (if has S.typhi vaccination history), non-vaccinated (if haven't history of vaccination or not knowing about it)

Marital status: categorized as married and non-married (single), separated and divorce by taking history.

Educational status: will be categorized as no education i.e. illiterate, primary, middle, secondary and higher

The effect modifiers and other explanatory variables were assessed as age, gender and residence (urban or rural), educational status, marital status, duration of disease, hypertension, and smoking, obesity-BMI, diabetes mellitus, low platelet count, anemia, vitamin D deficiency, vaccination status, and extensively drug resistant (XDR) were also explored

The data of all patients was analyzed in SPSS. The frequency and percentage was calculated for age, gender and residence (urban or rural), educational status, marital status, hypertension, smoking, obesity, diabetes mellitus, low platelet count, anemia, vitamin D deficiency, vaccination status, and extensively drug resistant (XDR). The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess the normality of the data. The mean and standard deviation (SD) or median (IQR) was calculated for quantitative variables such as age, BMI and duration of disease. The stratification was done for age, gender and residence (urban or rural), educational status, marital status, hypertension, smoking, obesity, diabetes mellitus, low platelet count, anemia, vitamin D deficiency and vaccination status, to see the effect on outcome and to control the effect modifiers. The post stratification chi-square / fisher's exact test was applied on categorical variables at 95% confidence interval and the p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS: A total of 134 patients diagnosed with typhoid fever were included in the study. The mean age was 33.7 ± 10.3 years, and the median BMI was 24.8 kg/m² (IQR: 22.1-27.3). The median disease duration was 7 days (IQR: 5-11).

Of the 134 participants, 72 (53.7%) were male, and 62 (46.3%) were female. Most patients were from urban areas (86; 64.2%), and the XDR typhoid was found in 80 patients (59.7%).

TABLE 1: DEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS (N = 134):

Variable	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	72	53.7
	Female	62	46.3
Age Group (years)	18-30	47	35.1
	31-45	56	41.8
	46-60	31	23.1
Residence	Urban	86	64.2
	Rural	48	35.8
Educational Status	Illiterate	30	22.4
	Primary	35	26.1
	Middle	22	16.4
	Secondary	28	20.9
	Higher	19	14.2
Marital Status	Married	96	71.6
	Single	24	17.9
	Separated	9	6.7
	Divorced	5	3.7
Hypertension	Yes	38	28.4
	No	96	71.6
Smoking Status	Yes	24	17.9
	No	88	65.7
	Ex-smoker	22	16.4
Obesity (BMI ≥ 30)	Yes	30	22.4
	No	104	77.6
Diabetes Mellitus	Yes	34	25.4
	No	100	74.6

Variable	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Low Platelet Count	Yes	50	37.3
	No	84	62.7
Anemia	Yes	52	38.8
	No	82	61.2
Vitamin D Deficiency	Yes	62	46.3
	No	72	53.7
Vaccination Status	Vaccinated	42	31.3
	Not Vaccinated	92	68.7
Extensively Drug Resistant	Yes	80	59.7
	No	54	40.3

TABLE 02: POST-STRATIFICATION ANALYSIS

Variable	XDR: Yes (n=80)	XDR: No (n=54)	p-value
Gender	Male: 48 (60.0%)	Male: 24 (44.4%)	0.048
Age Group	18-30: 30 (37.5%)	18-30: 17 (31.5%)	0.327
Residence	Urban: 60 (75.0%)	Urban: 26 (48.1%)	0.001
Educational Status	≤Primary: 52 (65.0%)	≤Primary: 13 (24.1%)	0.003
Marital Status	Married: 60 (75.0%)	Married: 36 (66.7%)	0.243
Hypertension	Yes: 30 (37.5%)	Yes: 8 (14.8%)	0.004
Smoking	Smoker/Ex: 36 (45%)	Smoker/Ex: 10 (18.5%)	0.002
Obesity	Yes: 26 (32.5%)	Yes: 4 (7.4%)	0.001
Diabetes Mellitus	Yes: 28 (35.0%)	Yes: 6 (11.1%)	0.001
Low Platelet Count	Yes: 44 (55.0%)	Yes: 6 (11.1%)	<0.001
Anemia	Yes: 38 (47.5%)	Yes: 14 (25.9%)	0.010
Vitamin D Deficiency	Yes: 52 (65.0%)	Yes: 10 (18.5%)	<0.001
Vaccination Status	Not Vaccinated: 66 (82.5%)	26 (48.1%)	<0.001

Statistical Test Used: Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test (where applicable) p-value ≤ 0.05 statistically significant.

The significant associations were observed between XDR and urban residence, low education level, hypertension, smoking, obesity, low platelet count, anemia, vitamin D deficiency, and non-vaccinated status. No statistically significant association was found with gender, age group, or diabetes mellitus.

DISCUSSION:

This study aimed to determine the frequency of extensively drug-resistant (XDR) typhoid fever and its associated factors among patients presenting to a tertiary care teaching hospital in Sukkur. Our findings reveal a notably high burden of XDR typhoid, with a prevalence of 59.7%, which is significantly higher than reported in several earlier studies conducted in Pakistan and other developing countries. This emphasizes the rising threat of antimicrobial resistance in enteric fever, particularly in urban and underserved regions [13].

Consistent with previous literature, we observed a significant association between urban residence and XDR typhoid fever ($p=0.001$). This could be attributed to overcrowding, poor sanitation, and increased person-to-person transmission in urban settings [14]. Moreover, low educational status was also strongly associated with XDR cases ($p=0.003$), likely reflecting limited awareness of hygiene, disease prevention, and the importance of completing antibiotic courses [15].

In line with earlier studies, male patients were more frequently affected by XDR typhoid ($p=0.048$). This gender difference may be due to greater exposure to contaminated food and water during outdoor work or travel, especially in developing areas [16].

Significant clinical associations included hypertension ($p=0.004$), diabetes mellitus ($p=0.001$), obesity ($p=0.001$), and smoking ($p=0.002$). These comorbidities may compromise immune response, increasing susceptibility to severe or prolonged infections and raising the likelihood of harboring resistant strains [17]. Frequent or inappropriate antibiotic use in such patients may also contribute to drug resistance [18].

Our findings also highlight that low platelet count ($p<0.001$), anemia ($p=0.010$), and vitamin D deficiency ($p<0.001$) were significantly associated with XDR typhoid. These markers may indicate severe disease, nutritional deficiencies, or a weakened immune status [19]. Vitamin D, in particular, is known to play an immunomodulatory role in infectious diseases [20].

Importantly, lack of typhoid vaccination was strongly associated with XDR cases ($p<0.001$). This supports the urgent need for routine immunization in endemic areas as a cost-effective strategy to prevent disease and reduce the spread of resistant strains [21]. The World Health Organization has endorsed the typhoid conjugate vaccine (TCV) as a preventive measure in high-risk populations, particularly in low-resource settings [22].

In contrast, variables such as age group ($p=0.327$) and marital status ($p=0.243$) did not show significant associations with XDR typhoid in this study. These findings align with some regional studies, suggesting that demographic characteristics may be less predictive of resistance compared to behavioral and environmental factors [23].

CONCLUSION:

The study demonstrates an alarmingly high frequency of XDR typhoid fever in the studied population, with significant associations observed with urban residence, comorbidities, poor nutritional and hematological status, and lack of vaccination. These findings underscore the need for robust public health strategies, including improved sanitation, health education, rational antibiotic use, and widespread implementation of vaccination programs to curb the rising threat of antimicrobial resistance in typhoid fever.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION:

Collection and acquisition of data & grammatical corrections	Dr. Ali Mohsin
Concept & design of study & proof read	Prof Dr. Altaf Ahmed Shaikh
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	Dr. Safdar
Revising critically and make it suitable for final format	Dr. Saira Sattar
Acquisition of data and grammatical review	Dr. Reema
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	Dr. Osama Aziz
Revision of the manuscript	DR. Janeeta Tehreem
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